

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
MINUTES OF THE BOARD OF STUDIES (BOS) MEETINGS
UG & PG COURSES

HELD ON 10/04/2021 AT 2PM IN THE CONFERENCE ROOM
CITY CAMPUS -SU

The meeting of the *Board of Studies (BOS) for UG & PG Courses of the College of Computer Science & Information Science* was held on **10/04/2021 at 2 PM** in SU City Campus - Conference Room, which was presided over by Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat – Dean of the College.

Sitting Members: -

(1) Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat	-	Chairman	
(2) Prof. P. Sridhara Acharya	-	Member	
(3) Prof. Vaikunth Pai	-	Member	
(4) Prof. Panchajanyeshwari Achar	-	Member	
(5) Prof. Krishnaprasad K	-	Member	
(6) Prof. Mangesh Nayak	-	Member	
(7) Mr. Shylesh S, SCDCC Bank, Mangaluru	-	External Member	
(8) Mr. Srinivas Rao, Software Administrator, Diya Systems, Mangalore	-	External Member	

Agenda

- **UG Courses and Syllabus**
- **PG Courses and Syllabus**
- **BOE for UG**
- **BOE for PG**
- **Any Other Matter**

The Gist of the meeting proceedings are as follows: -

Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat convened the meeting, welcomed all the sitting members, and addressed a few factors on action plans for the academic year 2021-22.

Resolution – 1:

Starting of new Credit based – Three-year (6 semesters) **BCA** program for the academic year 2021-22. Specialized subjects like Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality and Cloud Computing, Ethical Hacking, and Cyber Security and Data Science and Mobile Application related subjects were identified for each of the programs every semester and its detailed syllabus has been finalized after a thorough discussion with all the sitting members of BOS.

The existing BCA course syllabus also has been revised by considering the requirements of IT industries. Two courses each of 1 credit have been included in order to improve the employability skills among the students. The finalized syllabus has been sent to the registrar for final approval.

The new BCA course from the academic year 2021-22 has been updated according to NEP Syllabus in the following aspects compared to its previous year.

- 100 percent modification in the syllabus according to NEP Syllabus.
- The entire course syllabus is modified according to the credit-based system.
- According to NEP each semester contains 3 subject-oriented core subjects and 3 skill-enhanced subjects and 2 language subjects.

The NEP based syllabus for BCA 2021-22

Sl. No	Subject Code	Subject Name	Modification
1.	21CAC-1	Problem-solving using c	The focus is given to problem-solving methodology.
2	21CAC-2	Foundation of information technology	Unit III is modified modifying the concept of based programming language
3	21CAC-3	Basics of internet and web design	New subject.
4	21CAC-1P	LAB on Problem Solving using C	All programs changed.
5	21CAC-2P	Lab on the foundation of information systems	All exercises are modified.
6	21CAE-1	Information systems	The Unit IV having Advanced Written Communication is modified Research topics Journal writing Introduced
7	21CAC-4	Object-oriented programming	Only OOP Concepts are retained.
8	21CAC-5	Database management and MySQL	Relational data model is introduced

9	21CAC-6	Computer organization	Computer registers and counters
10	21CAC-4P	lab on object-oriented programming using c++	Quick sort is modified.
11	21CAC-5P	lab database management and MySQL	All programs changed.
12	21CAE-2	Introduction to electronic commerce	The basics of SDLC is introduced.
13	21CAC-7/SD	Programming in Core Java	The web interface for Servlets is modified.
14	21CAC-8/SD	HTML, VB Script and Java Script	Introduction to different types of Servers.
15	21CAC-9	Operating Systems	Kernel Architecture is modified
16	21CAC-7P	Lab on Programming in Core Java	All programs changed.
17	21CAC-8P	Lab on HTML, VB Script and Java Script	All programs changed.
18	21CAE-3	Open Elective-3	New subject introduced
19	21CAL1-3	English	New subject introduced
20	21CAL2/L3-3	Kannada/Hindi/French/Malayalam	New subject Introduced
21	21CAC10/	Advanced Java Programming	Web interface for Servlets is introduced.
22	1CAC11/SD	Web Technology	Importance of C# in programming
23	21CAC12/SD	E-Commerce	Introduction to Firewall is withdrawn. Different types of E payment
24	1CAC10P/SD	Lab on Advanced Java Programming	All programs changed.
25	21CAC11P/SD	Lab on Web Technology	Web interface for Servlets is modified.
26	21CAE-4	Open Elective-4	New subject introduced
27	21CAL1-4	English	New subject introduced
28	21CAL2/L3-4	Kannada/Hindi/French/Malayalam	New subject introduced
29	1CAC13/SD	Linux Environment	Monitor and Audit log is modified in cloud security
30	1CAC14/SD	Distributed Computing	SDLC need of SDLC, components, structure are introduced.
31	1CAC15/SD	Principles of TCP/IP	Comparison between IPv4 and IPv6
32	1CAC13P/SD	Lab on Linux Environment	All programs modified
33	21CAC14P/SD	Lab on Distributed Computing	All programs modified

34	21CAE-5	CA Elective-1	New subject introduced
35	21CAV-3	Vocational - 1	New subject introduced
36	1CAC 16/S D	LAMPTechnology	Apache Web Server Web based PHP database is introduced
37	21CAC 17/ SD	Application Programming in R	Software Configuration Management is introduced.
38	21CAC 18/ SD	Data Mining	Monitor and Audit log is modified in cloud security
39	16	Lab on LAMPTechnology	All programs modified
40	21CAC 17P/SD	Lab on Application Programming in R	All programs modified
41	21CAE-6	CA Elective-2	New subject introduced
42	21CAV-5	Vocational - 2	New subject introduced

Total Number of Papers in BCA 42

Total modifications are done **All subjects are modified according to NEP Syllabus.**
Percentage of Modifications **100%**

Resolution – 2:

Based on the feedback from various stakeholders of the institution, the existing MCA course syllabus has been revised for the academic year 2021-22, by considering the requirements of IT industries. Specialized courses were identified for these programs every semester and its detailed syllabus has been finalized after a thorough discussion with all the sitting members of BOS. It has been decided to call industry experts in order to deliver some identified courses of MCA. Two courses each of 1 credit have been included in order to improve the employability skills among the students. The finalized syllabus has been sent to the registrar for final approval.

The new MCA course from the academic year 2021-22 has been updated in the following aspects compare to its previous year.

MCA 2021-22

Sl. No	Subject Code	Subject Name	Modification
1.	21MCA13	Web Frameworks	Angular and node JS included in III and IV unit
2.	21MCA151	Statistics for Data Science	The application part of statistics is introduced in the V unit
4.	21MCA142	Introduction to Cyber Security and Cyber Law	Disaster Recovery, Personnel Security topics are included in the IV unit
5.	21MCA153	Ethical Hacking	Hacking Mobile Platforms, Android Hacking, and Mobile Device Management topics are included in the V unit
6.	21MCA242	Network and Web Application Security	The DevOps Approach topic is included in V unit
7.	21MCA252	Cryptography Blockchain technology	Blockchain technology topics are included in IV and V unit
8.	21MCA383	Cyber Forensics	Case studies are updated in IV unit
9.	21MCA353	Security Incident and Compliance Management	Vendor Risk Management, Reporting topics are included in V unit

15

Total Number of Papers in MCA:

Total modifications are done in terms of paper 32

Approximate Percentage of Modifications: 28%

Resolution – 4:

Nomination to Member for BOE-UG

The following members have been nominated as members of BOE in UG, for the academic year 2021-2022.

(1) Prof. Netravathi P S

(2) Ms. Anusha Rai

Members of BOE - UG

Academic (internal):

(1) Mr. Mangesh Nayak - Chairman

(2) Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat - Member

(3) Prof. Vaikunta Pai - Member

(4) Prof. Sridhara Acharya - Member

(5) Panchajanyeshwari Achar - Member

(6) Prof. Krishnaprasad K - Member

(7) Mr. Shylesh S - Member

(8) Mrs. Chaitra B S - Member

(9) Mr. Pradeep M D - Member

(10) Mr. Varun Shenoy - Member

(11) Mrs. Pavitra Kumari - Member

(12) Prof. Netravathi P S - Member

(13) Ms. Anusha Rai - Member

Resolution – 5:

Nomination to Members for BOE-PG

Following member have been nominated as members of BOE in PG, for the academic year 2021-2022.

(1) Prof. Netravathi P S

Members of BOE - PG

Academic (internal):

(1) Prof. Vaikunta Pai - Chairman

(2) Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat - Member

(3) Prof. Panchajanyeshwari Achar - Member

(4) Prof. Sridhara Acharya - Member

(5) Dr. Krishnaprasad K - Member

(6) Mr. Shylesh - Member

(8) Mr. Pradeep M D - Member

(9) Mr. Varun Shenoy - Member

(10) Prof. Netravathi P S - Member

In addition, it has been decided to call identified industry experts also as examiners for some courses in **MCA & BCA**

Resolution – 6:

Non-credit certificate courses for BCA and MCA programs: Based on request and demand from the student side department is decided to start a certification program for BCA and MCA programs. For BCA we plan to start a certification program entitled Hardware and Networking and for MCA we plan to start a certification program entitled Data Science Using Python.

Resolution – 7:

Other Related Matters

The members also discussed various other related matters about the forthcoming Academic Examinations, the Scheme of Valuation and Question Bank, and starting non-credit certification programs for BCA and MCA, etc. The meeting ended after a detailed discussion, questions & answers including certain clarifications on the above points and finally, a vote of thanks to all present was extended by Prof. PSA.

cc: Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University
Registrar, Srinivas University
Registrar (Evaluation), Srinivas University

Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat

Prof. Sridhara Acharya

Prof. Vaikunth Pai

Prof. Panchajanyeshwari Achar

Prof. Krishnaprasad K

Mr. Shylesh

Mr. Srinivas Rao

Mr. G.K Bhat

Mr. Mangesh Nayak

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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MINUTES OF THE BOARD OF STUDIES (BOS) MEETINGS
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HELD ON 15/10/2021 AT 2PM IN THE CONFERENCE ROOM
CITY CAMPUS -SU

The meeting of the *Board of Studies (BOS) for UG & PG Courses of the College of Computer Science & Information Science* was held on **15/11/2021 at 2 PM** in SU City Campus - Conference Room, which was presided over by Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat – Dean of the College.

Sitting Members: -

(1) Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat	-	Chairman	
(2) Prof. P. Sridhara Acharya	-	Member	
(3) Prof. Vaikunth Pai	-	Member	
(4) Prof. Panchajanyeshwari Achar	-	Member	
(5) Prof. Krishnaprasad K	-	Member	
(6) Dr. Netravathi P S	-	Member	
(7) Prof. Mangesh Nayak	-	Member	
(7) Mr. Shylesh S, SCDCC Bank, Mangaluru	-	External Member	
(8) Mr. Srinivas Rao, Software Administrator, Diya Systems, Mangalore	-	External Member	
(9) Mr. Praveen Kalbavi – CEO, Novigo Solutions Mangaluru	-	External Member	
(10) Mr. Krishnaraja – CEO, Vidita Solutions Mangaluru	-	External Member	

Agenda

- **BOE for UG**
- **Any Other Matter**

The Gist of the meeting proceedings are as follows: -

Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat convened the meeting, welcomed all the sitting members, and addressed a few factors on action plans for the academic year 2021-22.

Resolution – 7:

Amendment for BOE - UG

With regard to the nomination for the new Chairman & Members of the **BOE-UG**, the members nominated the following member with roles specified below.

Academic:

(1) Prof. Sridhara Acharya	-	Chairman
(2) Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat	-	Member
(3) Prof. Vaikunth Pai	-	Member
(4) Dr. Krishnaprasad	-	Member
(5) Panchajanyeshwari Achar	-	Member
(6) Prof. Vikranth K	-	Member
(7) Mrs. Harshitha	-	Member

- | | | |
|------|----------------------|----------|
| (8) | Mrs. Priyadarshini | - Member |
| (9) | Mr. Pradeep M D | - Member |
| (10) | Mr. Varun Shenoy | - Member |
| (11) | Mrs. Pavitra Kumari | - Member |
| (12) | Prof. Netravathi P S | - Member |
| (13) | Ms. Anusha Rai | - Member |
| (14) | Mr. Vittal Shenoy | - Member |
| (15) | Mrs. Jitha | - Member |

In addition, it has been decided to call identified industry experts also as examiners for some courses in **BCA, MCA**

Resolution – 8: Amendment for BOE - PG

The following member has been nominated as members of BOE in PG, for the academic year 2021-2022.

Academic

- | | | |
|-----|-------------------------------|------------|
| (1) | Prof. Vaikunta Pai | - Chairman |
| (2) | Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat | - Member |
| (3) | Prof. Panchajanyeshwari Achar | - Member |
| (4) | Prof. Sridhara Acharya | - Member |
| (5) | Dr. Krishnaprasad K | - Member |
| (6) | Dr. Netravathi P S | - Member |
| (8) | Mr. Pradeep M D | - Member |
| (9) | Mr. Varun Shenoy | - Member |

In addition, it has been decided to call identified industry experts also as examiners for the **MCA course**.

Resolution – 9: Other Related Matters

The members also discussed various other related matters about the forthcoming Academic Examinations, the Scheme of the Valuation Question Bank, etc. The meeting ended after a detailed discussion, questions & answers including certain clarifications on the above points and finally, a vote of thanks to all present was extended by Prof. Vaikunth Pai.

cc: Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University
Registrar, Srinivas University
Registrar (Evaluation), Srinivas University

Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat

Prof. Sridhara Acharya

Prof. Vaikunth Pai

Prof. Netravathi PS

Prof. Krishnaprasad K

Mr. Shylsh

Mr. Srinivas Rao

Mr. Praveen Kalbavi

Mr. Krishnaraja

**REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSIT
MANGALORE**

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
MINUTES OF THE BOARD OF STUDIES (BOS) MEETINGS
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HELD ON 20/11/2021 AT 2PM IN THE CONFERENCE ROOM
CITY CAMPUS -SU

The meeting of the *Board of Studies (BOS) for UG & PG Courses of the College of Computer Science & Information Science* was held on **20/10/2021 at 2PM** in SU City Campus - Conference Room, which was presided over by Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat – Dean of the College.

Sitting Members: -

(1) Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat	-	Chairman	
(2) Prof. P. Sridhara Acharya	-	Member	
(3) Prof. Vaikunth Pai	-	Member	
(4) Prof. Panchajanyeshwari Achar	-	Member	
(5) Prof. Krishnaprasad K	-	Member	
(6) Dr. Netravathi P S	-	Member	
(7) Prof. Mangesh Nayak	-	Member	
(7) Mr. Shylesh S, SCDCC Bank, Mangaluru	-	External Member	
(8) Mr. Srinivas Rao, Software Administrator, Diya Systems, Mangalore	-	External Member	
(9) Mr. Praveen Kalbavi – CEO, Novigo Solutions Mangaluru	-	External Member	
(10) Mr. Krishnaraja – CEO, Vidita Solutions Mangaluru	-	External Member	

Agenda

- **Restructuring the UG programs for the academic year 2021-22 as per NEP 2020 policy.**
- **Any Other Matter**

The Gist of the meeting proceedings are as follows: -

Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat convened the meeting, welcomed all the sitting member,s and addressed few factors on restructuring UG programs for the academic year 2021-22 under NEP 2020 policy.

Resolution – 10:

The UG program BCA was restructured according to the new education policy NEP 2020. Henceforth, the university will be offering BCA honours degrees including of total **208 credits**. The first year of UG programs has been designed with a total of **56 credits**, where Students are given the exit option with a **Certificate program on Computer Application/Science**.

The second year of UG programs has been designed with a total of **56 credits**, where Students are given the exit option after completing two years of UG programs with a **Diploma Certificate on Computer Application/Science** having total **112 credits**.

The Third year of UG programs has been designed with a total **50 credits**, where in Students are given the exit option after completing three years of UG programs with a Degree **Bachelor of Computer Application/Science** having total **162 credits**.

The Fourth year of UG programs has been designed with a total **46 credits**, where in Students after completing Four years of UG programs will be awarded a Honer's Degree in **Bachelor of Computer Application/Science** having total **208 credits**.

Various committees were formed to finalize Core courses, Open Electives, and Computer Application Electives ALONG WITH Base courses as per NEP policy, and its syllabus contents were finalized to submit to the Registrar's office for approval.

**Resolution – 11:
Other Related Matters**

The members discussed Language courses to be considered in different semesters of UG programs as per NEP 2020 and finalized. The detailed syllabus of UG courses was finalized after mutual discussions. The finalized course structure and syllabus have been sent in a separate document for the Registrar's office to get approval. Also discussed other related matters about the forthcoming Academic Examinations, Scheme of Valuation Question Bank, etc.

The meeting ended after a detailed discussion, questions & answers including certain clarifications on the above points and finally a vote of thanks to all present was extended by Dr. Netravathi PS.

cc: Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University
Registrar, Srinivas University
Registrar (Evaluation), Srinivas University

Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat

Prof. Sridhara Acharya

Prof. Vaikunth Pai

Prof. Netravathi PS

Prof. Krishnaprasad K

Mr. Shylesh

Mr. Srinivas Rao

Mr. Praveen Kalbavi

Mr. Krishnaraja

*Reviewed
The next will be put up in
Academic Council!*

**REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
BANGALORE**